

A Study on Digital Recruitment Strategies

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Abstract

The world exists at the interaction between the old world and new, the crosswords of human interaction and daily digital advancement. Digital recruitment is a part of the sector leading to charge, offering enticing hikes of 30-40% for in-demand talent, around half a dozen headhunters and recruitment firms. Digital recruitment plays the role of the middleman connecting job seekers and employers in a time efficient manner in the comfort of their own space. The main purpose of the paper is to analyze how new technology has influenced the recruitment process as a whole.

Introduction

If one wants to buy a mobile phone, how would he proceed? He would not run an advertisement in the newspaper telling people he's looking for a mobile phone and wait for a good one to turn up at his house. He would visit a variety of local showrooms where the mobile phones are, to find what he's looking for. He'd identify where the phones he's interested in are located and visit those locations. This analogy is applicable to how human resource departments attract and recruit agile talent to their organizations. Recruitment refers to the overall process of attracting, short listing, selecting and appointing suitable candidates for jobs within an organization. One of the most current methods of recruiting is digital recruiting, accessible 24 hours a day and 7 days a week. Digital recruitment is when modern technology is used to hire human resources. "Twenty years ago the resume was just a piece of paper. But now it is a collection of all data that can be found online" says Jon Bischke, CEO of Entelo. Nearly 30% of all Google searches are employment related. E-recruiting is not just a fad. It is embedded, ensuring that we are moving with the time.

Methods of Digital Recruitment

Direct Digital Recruitment

Direct recruitment eliminates any middlemen in the process of sourcing new talent for an organization, the paradigm case being on-campus recruitment by an employer's in-house recruiters.

1. Social network: Many companies hire through social networking websites such as LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube and Facebook. Social network recruiting demonstrates that companies can find

the best talent quickly without vast financial investment. It allows employers to screen potential employees without being screened. When a candidate who interests the employer is active on social networks, he can glean a lot about how the candidate works with others, how he handles customers, conflicts and much more. All of which helps the employer see who may be a great fit for the company, thereby increasing the chances of longer retention.

2. Recruiting blogs: Recruiting blogs allow the company to show a potential employee what it, as an organization is like. Blogs conversely allow job seekers to check companies out, rather than the other way round. They allow employers to exhibit their zeal. While a company website simply serves up an often unchanging chunk of information, a Blog on the other hand, gives the employers the chance to embark their take on the issues of the day, giving a candid view of what the company actually is.

Indirect Digital Recruitment

In indirect digital recruitment, employers rely on consultancy firms to recruit potential employees using the digital platform. The companies put to use the services of third parties to enjoy hassle-free recruitment process. The third parties are experts that provide professional feedback on potential candidates to an organization for a fee.

1. Virtual job fairs: Virtual job fairs offer an intuitive, engaging and interactive process exactly like a traditional job fair but within a virtual environment. They allow employers to interact with job seekers on a virtual level without the time and expense of travel and it enables the company to reach a larger number of potential employees from a larger geographical area.
2. Online recruitment sites: These is the most well known of the digital recruitment methods but it continues to improve on its offering day by day to ensure its service stands head and shoulders above the rest. Monster for instance is the leading provider of online careers and recruitment resources, connecting organizations in every segment of the market with individuals at every career level globally.

Literature Review- Methods Of Literature

Lievens F. and Harris M. (2003) acknowledged that for practitioners and researchers, the application of new technologies such as internet recruitment and testing is both exciting and challenging.

Prabjot Kaur (2015) concluded that as the use of internet is indispensable, physical boundaries are blending and when it comes to professional mobility and the hunt for talented and skilled workforce at peak level in regional economics, the medium is definitely here to stay for long.

Rozy Rani (2016) stated that it is a time saving and cost effective method and that the internet has been accepted as most convenient tool to find jobs

Pikala and Jussi-Pekka (2017) concluded that it seemed that the actual HR professionals had a better knowledge of the digital tools and small companies with the actual HR department not being familiar with the digital tools.

Piana Monsur Minda and Md. Kazimul Hoque (2018) stated that as an initial step of improvement, the management should also train the recruiters adequately for building an effective system for online recruitment in the organizations

Digital Recruiting Strategies

1. Establish company's online reputation: A company can influence its reputation positively by being active on social media, writing a blog with professional and inspirational content. Sharing the company's achievements and awards on social media is also a boost in the company's reputation as candidates are attracted to experienced, successful and award-winning companies.

2. Leverage social media: Employers who used social media to hire found a 49% improvement in candidate quality over candidates sourced only through traditional recruiting channels. Social media is also an excellent channel to spread brand awareness. Apart from scouring websites, millennials look to social media channels to gather more information about the company. The first step to social recruiting is to create the company's own social recruiting universe and discern where the targeted candidates are present. Creating a recruiting strategy to engage and convert active and passive talent on these channels escalates the leverage of the company in social media.
3. LinkedIn profile: 87% of recruiters use LinkedIn, which makes it the top social network of choice in terms of finding skilled candidates. Though LinkedIn is a somewhat specialized platform, its prominence in the world of recruiting top talent will continue being high throughout
4. 2019. Participation in LinkedIn groups is important. The social network has a huge number of specialized communities that attract experts in specific fields. When the company is active in relevant groups it is much easier to identify both top talent and influencers. Such information can be invaluable when it comes to attracting the right professionals in a highly competitive niche.
5. Artificial Intelligence: When it comes to recruiting techniques Artificial Intelligence is already playing a huge role in the way businesses find new talent. AI for recruitment is an emerging strategy in the human resource technology to shortlist the candidates automatically, rather than screening it manually. AI startups are significantly reducing the operational burden by automating low level tasks and providing better information for decision makers.
6. Mobile friendly career website: It's more important than ever to not only have a visible presence via the career site, but also to make it user-friendly and a notable part of enhancing that user experience is ensuring the career site is mobile friendly. Candidates use an average of 16 different sources to search for jobs and 4 in 5 of those candidates will visit a company's career site during their job search process. More than half of companies have websites that are not optimized for mobile devices, which could work against them. The best way to ensure a quality mobile experience and keep candidates engaged on the company's career site is through responsive design.
7. Video Interviews: Video interviews are an increasingly popular tool in talent acquisition because of their ability to save time and money involved in traditional, in-person interviews; remove geographic constraints; automate candidates screening; and improve the quality of data. They are used at many stages of the hiring process. Synchronous interviews are conducted live over the internet and are often used as an alternative to an in-person interview. In contrast asynchronous video interviews are recorded by the job seeker at the time convenient to them. This is the least expensive approach and generally easy to set up.

Research Objectives

Objective of the Study

In this study we propose the different strategies used for employing people through the digital platform.

Scope of the Study

- It is time and cost effective
- It helps to reach a bigger audience
- The job ad can be made more dynamic
- It expedites the hiring process
- It helps to shortlist qualified candidates the globe

Limitations

- It attracts bad candidates and fraudulent applicants
- The major drawback is people in rural areas are unaware of it
- There is a lot of competition forcing the company to pay more for extra exposure

Research Methodology

A Questionnaire was prepared for the primary data collection. Multiple choices were given below the questions that were framed relevant to the topic. A sample size of 60 respondents has been used for this research. Normal sampling technique was used for analyzing the data.

Findings and Analysis

Q1) Are you aware of digital recruitment?

Q2) Have you ever visited an online recruitment site?

Yes	48.3%
No	51.7%

Q3) Which method of digital recruitment do you prefer?

Social media	36.7%
Recruiting blogs	8.3%
Virtual job fairs	15%
Online recruitment sites	38.3%
others	1.7%

Q4) What is your overall opinion on digital recruitment?

Q5) If you were to choose between digital and non digital recruitment, which would you choose?

Findings

Through this research it is found that 81.7% of the respondents encourage digital recruitment which indicates that recruiters are slowly migrating into the digital realm, digital recruitment is growing to become the preferred means of talent scouting. From the above data analysis, it has also been interpreted that 55% of the respondents go for digital recruitment and their overall opinion on digital recruitment is beyond average. Digital recruiting methods used to hire has found an improvement in candidate quality over candidates sourced only through traditional recruiting channels and a time and cost effective method for job seekers as they can find the advertisements easily on websites, job boards and portals. Amongst the strategies, online recruitment sites followed by social media were found to be the prominent ones.

Conclusion

Traditional recruiting has passed the baton to digital. The time has come to adapt to transition from dinosaur recruiting strategies to technology-backed modern ones. The use of modern technologies in the recruitment processes is not just another trend in the changing environment, it will permanently appear in the area of human resources. The significant potential in the field of artificial intelligence and machine learning has been proven many times, HR industry still has a long way to go in order to fully utilise them. By not utilizing them, companies are not only letting go of the opportunity to attract quality talent but also relinquishing the chance to reduce the burden on recruiters.